

Equivalence Classes and Discernibility in Power Graphs

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we study indiscernibility partitions and cardinality of each indiscernibility partition of power graph $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}$, $s_i \geq 1$. The emerging theory of rough set is applied on power graph $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ of a finite group \mathcal{Z}_m using the concept of open and closed neighborhood. We define the indiscernibility relations in terms of neighborhood and discuss necessary and sufficient conditions for indiscernibility partitions. We study granular computing techniques using information systems. Further, we study rough approximations, rough membership function, discernibility matrix, reduct, core, essential sets and some topological properties.

Keywords: Information System, Indiscernibility Classes, Roughness, Topological Properties

1. Introduction

The goal of granular computing (GrC) is to aggregate data for representation and processing. Data abstraction and knowledge extraction lead to the emergence of aggregates that are frequently referred to as information granules or simply granules. Groups of things that have same characteristic such as resemblance, functionality, closeness, indistinguishability, coherency, etc., are said to be information granules. The term granular computing is used to refer to a wide variety of research areas that focus on the representation and extraction of knowledge. Information granularity was first suggested by Zadeh in [61] in 1979 as part of his study of fuzzy sets. Again, in

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1997 [60], Zadeh used the phrase granular computing, this time defining it as, granular computing is a subset of computing with words. Since its start in 1979, granular computing has grown into a robust field of study in the theoretical and practical realms of information science [5, 30]. Interval analysis [23], machine learning [53], data mining [5, 25, 46, 56, 18], database theory [18, 39], formal concept analysis [52], interactive computing [44, 45], rough set theory [38, 37], and fuzzy set theory [29] all intersect and find application in modern GrC, which has emerged as a distinct research area in the field of knowledge management.

The component of granular computing related to information systems and their management using rough sets tools is the focus of this thesis. An information system or table, abbreviated as I , is the bi-dimensional that associates a value for each attribute under examination with any item. The information system is said to be Boolean if all of the assigned values are 0 or 1. An information table is a frequent structure in a variety of quantitative and qualitative fields of research. In addition to his seminal work in rough set theory [37], Pawlak provided many analytical tools for dissecting and streamlining a generic information table. Simply put, if we have two objects and they have same values $\forall a \in \mathcal{A}$ then these objects are \mathcal{A} -indiscernible. The indiscernibility relation is represented by $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}$, where \mathcal{A} is any attribute subset. Since $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{A}}$ is an equivalence relation, the large portion of Pawlak's theory may be seen as a special case of granular computing in the future GrC-RS [57]. At least four concepts in GrC-RS deserve special attention: the indiscernibility relations, the core, the reduct family, and the discernibility matrix. If you think about the attributes that define a information table, the core [3] is probably what you value most. To completely define a table, the reduct which basically the special subset of attributes contain enough information. Lastly, the set of attributes that differentiate objects u_i and u_j in the (i, j) direction is stored in a square matrix called the discernibility matrix. Since decades, the integration of rough set theory and graph theory has been a rapidly developing area of research. Shahzamanian in [43] investigated roughness in Cayley graphs. The use of a rough set in graph theory was first introduced by Chen and Li [7]. Graph theory and rough sets were brought together by Chiaselotti [33]. The Chiaselotti also investigated simple graphs in the context of formal concept analysis, n -cycle and n -path graphs in term of rough sets [10, 11, 12]. Silva [11] investigated rough approximation for n -cycles and n -paths. Mathew [39] introduced the idea of vertex rough graphs.

A graph \mathcal{G} is composed of two finite sets $\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{G})$ and $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G})$ where, $\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{G})$ is called set of vertices or nodes and $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G})$ is known as set of edges. Actually, the set of edges is the cartesian product of different ordered pair of vertices i.e; $E \subseteq \mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V}$. We can also call edges as links. A power graph $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ is a graph in which two vertices namely α and β are neighbor of each others if one of them is the power of other. Several graph constructions may be found in the literature that start with groups or semigroups [6] including intersection graphs of sub-semi-groups or sub-groups, and of course Cayley graphs, which have a broader history. Kelarev and Quinn [21, 22] defined the directed power graph of a semigroup S as the digraph $G(S)$ with vertex set S , in which there is an arc from u to v if and only if $v \neq u$ and $v = u^m$ for any positive integer m . Chakrabarty et al. [22] were inspired by this and created the (undirected) power graph

$G(S)$, in which separate α and β are linked if one is a power of the other. Abawajy [1] surveyed the field of power graphs in 2013 and reported findings on their eulerian, hamiltonian, and exhaustive characterization. They also compiled and shared information on power graphs edge counts, chromatic numbers, planarity, and isomorphism. Nonetheless, the authors did not delve into topics like connectedness, spectral analysis, or power graph automorphisms.

By linking rough sets and power graphs, rough set properties can be understood using power graphs and power graphs properties can be explained using rough sets. Information granules can provide important insights about graphs, enriching their applications in various fields and introducing new perspectives to obtain knowledge patterns using different attribute sets. We classified the power graph of a finite \mathcal{Z}_n in order to study the behavior of vertices in different classes. In other words, a strategy developed in one domain can provide insight into another.

2. Information System

In rough set, data is displayed by a table known as information table. The columns represents attributes set whereas rows represent the objects of finite universal set. The information table, typically in a rough set, is commonly referred to as an information system denoted as \mathcal{I} . A quadruple $\mathcal{I} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{V}, \phi)$ is known as information system, where \mathcal{U} is a finite universe set, \mathcal{A} represents attribute set and ϕ is a mapping, $\phi: \mathcal{U} \times \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{V}$ such that $\phi(x, a) = \mathcal{V}, \forall a \in \mathcal{A}$.

Definition 2.1 Let $(\mathcal{G}, *)$ be a group, $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{G}$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} , then quadruple $\mathcal{I} = \langle \mathcal{G}, \mathcal{G}, \{0,1\}, \phi \rangle$ is known as Boolean information system, where $\phi: \mathcal{G} \times \mathcal{G} \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ is define as follows:

$$\phi(\alpha, \beta) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \alpha = \beta^n \text{ or } \beta = \alpha^m \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

3. Indiscernibility Partitions of Power Graphs

We divide this section into two subsections using the relation of open and closed neighborhood.

3.1 Indiscernibility Partitions Using Open Neighborhood

Suppose $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a group \mathcal{G} and $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{G}$, then indiscernibility of two vertices α and β is defined as; $\alpha \equiv_{\mathcal{G}} \beta \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{N}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}(\beta)$. Similarly, for attribute set $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{G}$. $\alpha \equiv_{\mathcal{A}} \beta \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \cap \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{N}(\beta) \cap \mathcal{A}$. Equivalently, $\alpha \equiv_{\mathcal{A}} \beta \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{F}(\alpha, a) = \mathcal{F}(\beta, a), \forall a \in \mathcal{A}$.

Theorem 3.1 Let $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ having vertex set \mathcal{G} and $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{G}$. Let $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{G}$. Then the following statements are equivalent.

- (1) $\alpha \equiv_{\mathcal{A}} \beta$.
- (2) $\forall \gamma \in \mathcal{A}, \alpha = \gamma^k \text{ or } \gamma = \alpha^n \text{ iff } \beta = \gamma^l \text{ or } \gamma = \beta^n$.
- (3) $\mathcal{N}(\alpha) \cap \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{N}(\beta) \cap \mathcal{A}$.

Proof: (1) \Rightarrow (2) Let $\gamma \in \mathcal{A}$ and $\alpha \equiv_{\mathcal{A}} \beta$. Suppose $\alpha = \gamma^n$ and we are required to show that $\beta = \gamma^m$. By (1) we have that $\mathcal{F}(\alpha, a) = \mathcal{F}(\beta, a), \forall a \in \mathcal{A}$, therefore

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$\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \gamma) = \mathcal{F}(\beta, \gamma)$. Since $\alpha = \gamma^n$, therefore by definition 2.1 we have $\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \gamma) = 1$ and hence $\mathcal{F}(\beta, \gamma) = 1$, that is $\beta = \gamma^m$. Now by symmetry of $\equiv_{\mathcal{A}}$, if we assume that $\beta = \gamma^m$ we can obtain $\alpha = \gamma^n$. It proves (ii).

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii) We are given $\forall \gamma \in \mathcal{A}, \alpha = \gamma^n$ if and only if $\beta = \gamma^m$, and we are to prove that $\mathcal{N}(\alpha) \cap \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{N}(\beta) \cap \mathcal{A}$. Now by symmetricity of (ii) it is sufficient to prove $\mathcal{N}(\alpha) \cap \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{N}(\beta) \cap \mathcal{A}$. Now let $\mathcal{N}(\alpha) \cap \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{N}(\beta) \cap \mathcal{A}$, then $\alpha = \gamma^n$ and $x \in \mathcal{A}$. By (ii) we have if $\alpha = \gamma^n$ then $\beta = \gamma^m$. Hence $\gamma \in \mathcal{N}(\beta) \cap \mathcal{A}$. Thus, $\mathcal{N}(\alpha) \cap \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{N}(\beta) \cap \mathcal{A}$. (iii) \Rightarrow (i) Let $\gamma \in \mathcal{A}$. We are required to show that $\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \gamma) = \mathcal{F}(\beta, \gamma)$. Now

$$\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \gamma) = \mathcal{F}(\beta, \gamma) \Leftrightarrow (\alpha = \gamma^n \Leftrightarrow \beta = \gamma^m) \quad (1)$$

Then, if $\alpha = \gamma^n$, we have $\gamma \in \mathcal{N} \cap \mathcal{A}$, then by (iii) $\gamma \in \mathcal{N} \cap \mathcal{A}$. Hence $\gamma \in \mathcal{N}$, that is $\beta = \gamma^m$. Analogously, by symmetry of (iii). if $\beta = \gamma^m$, then $\alpha = \gamma^n$. By (1) we deduce that $\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \gamma) = \mathcal{F}(\beta, \gamma)$. Since $\gamma \in \mathcal{A}$ is arbitrary, this proves (i).

Definition 3.1 Let $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be power graph of a group \mathcal{G} . Then the class of vertex α is defined as:

$$C(\alpha) = \{\beta \in \mathcal{V} | \mathcal{N}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}(\beta)\}, \text{ and for } \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{V} \quad C_{\mathcal{A}}(\beta) = \{\beta \in \mathcal{V} | \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \cap \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{N}(\beta) \cap \mathcal{A}\}.$$

Also suppose $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph. Then the subset $S(\mathcal{Z}_m)$ of \mathcal{V} is said to be saturated if and only if it consists of those vertices that are adjacent to all other vertices. Mathematically,

$$S(\mathcal{Z}_m) = \{\alpha: \gcd(\alpha, m) = 1; 1 \leq \alpha < m\} \cup \{0\}.$$

Proposition 3.2 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}, s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph. Let $\mathcal{A} = \{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_k\}$ be a saturated subset of $\mathcal{G} = \{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m\}$ then $\pi_{\mathcal{A}} = \alpha_1 | \alpha_2 | \dots | \alpha_k | \mathcal{A}^c$, where \mathcal{A}^c is the complement of \mathcal{A} in \mathcal{G} .

Proof: Let $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{G}$, with $\alpha \neq \beta$. Since $\alpha = \beta^n$ by theorem 3.2.1, it shows that if $\alpha \equiv_{\mathcal{A}} \beta$, then $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{A}^c$. On the other hand, if $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{A}^c$, then since \mathcal{A} is saturated $\forall \gamma \in \mathcal{A}$, by definition 2.1 $\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \gamma) = \mathcal{F}(\beta, \gamma) = 1$, it means that $\alpha \equiv_{\mathcal{A}} \beta$. This proves the result.

Example 3.3 Let $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_{10}$ with vertex set $\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{G}) = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 9\}$ and $\mathcal{A} = \{0, 1, 3, 7, 9\}$ saturated subset of \mathcal{G} . Then we have,

$$\mathcal{N}(0) \cap \mathcal{A} = \{1, 3, 7, 9\}, \quad \mathcal{N}(1) \cap \mathcal{A} = \{0, 3, 7, 9\}, \quad \mathcal{N}(3) \cap \mathcal{A} = \{0, 1, 7, 9\}, \quad \mathcal{N}(7) \cap \mathcal{A} = \{0, 1, 3, 7\}$$

$$\mathcal{N}(9) \cap \mathcal{A} = \{0, 1, 3, 7\}, \quad \mathcal{N}(2) \cap \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{N}(4) \cap \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{N}(5) \cap \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{N}(6) \cap \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{N}(8) \cap \mathcal{A} = \{0, 1, 3, 7, 9\}.$$

Thus $\pi_{\mathcal{A}}(\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})) = 0 | 1 | 3 | 7 | 9 | \{2, 4, 5, 6, 8\}$.

Proposition 3.4 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}, s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph, then $|\pi_{\mathcal{V}}| = m$.

Proof: Given $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}, s_i \geq 1$. Then $\mathcal{N}(\alpha) \neq \mathcal{N}(\beta)$, for all $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{G}$. Therefore we get m indiscernibility classes.

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Proposition 3.5 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}$, $s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph. Let \mathcal{A} contains any of singleton saturated vertex α . Then its indiscernibility is $\pi_{\mathcal{A}}(\mathcal{G}) = \alpha|\mathcal{V}\backslash\alpha$.

Proof: If \mathcal{A} contains only singleton saturated vertex α , then $\mathcal{N}(\alpha) \cap \mathcal{A} = \phi$ and $\mathcal{N}(\beta_i \backslash \alpha) = \{\alpha\}$. Therefore we have two blocks, i.e $\pi_{\mathcal{A}}(\mathcal{G}) = \alpha|\beta_i \backslash \alpha$.

Remark 3.1 Let $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_{2p}$, where p is prime and let $\mathcal{A} = \{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_k\}$ be a saturated subset of $\mathcal{G} = \{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n\}$. Then $|\pi_{\mathcal{A}}| = k + 1$.

Example 3.6 Consider $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_{10}$. Here we have saturated subset $\mathcal{A} = \{0,1,3,7,9\}$ and we have $\pi_{\mathcal{A}} = 0|1|3|7|9|2,4,5,6,8$. Thus $|\pi_{\mathcal{A}}| = 6$

Remark 3.2 Let $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_{2p}$ having vertex set \mathcal{G} and $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{G} \backslash \mathcal{A}$ and $\alpha \sim \beta$ then, $\alpha \equiv_{\mathcal{A}} \beta$ if \mathcal{A} is the saturated subset of \mathcal{G} .

Remark 3.3 Let $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_{2p}$, where p is any prime. Let $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{G}$ and $\alpha \sim \beta$ then $\alpha \not\equiv_{\mathcal{A}} \beta$ iff $\mathcal{N}(\alpha) \cap \mathcal{A} \neq \mathcal{N}(\beta) \cap \mathcal{A}$.

Proposition 3.7 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}$, $s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} . If $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{G}$ then, $\pi_{\mathcal{A}} = \alpha_1|\alpha_2|\dots|\alpha_n$.

Proof: It can be prove similarly by proposition 0.3.5.

Further, we discuss about indiscernibility partitions of power graphs using the relation of closed neighborhood.

3.2 Indiscernibility Partitions of Power Graphs using Closed Neighborhood

Let \mathcal{G} be a group and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph and $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{G}$, then indiscernibility of two vertices α and β is defined as; $\alpha \equiv_{\mathcal{G}} \beta \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{N}[\alpha] = \mathcal{N}[\beta]$. Similarly, for attribute set $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{G}$, $\alpha \equiv_{\mathcal{A}} \beta \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{N}[\alpha] \cap \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{N}[\beta] \cap \mathcal{A}$.

Equivalently $\alpha \equiv_{\mathcal{A}} \beta \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{F}(\alpha, \gamma) = \mathcal{F}(\beta, \gamma), \forall \gamma \in \mathcal{A}$.

Proposition 3.8 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}$, $s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} . Then we have $|\pi_{\mathcal{G}}| = \prod_{i=1}^m (s_i + 1) - 1$.

Proof: Given $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}$, $s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} . Since one block of $\pi_{\mathcal{G}}$ consists of saturated vertices, i.e. $\mathcal{B}_1 = \{\alpha | \gcd(\alpha, m) = 1, \forall \alpha \in \mathcal{G}\} \cup \{0\}$. There are $\frac{m!}{(m-1)!}$ blocks represented as $\mathcal{B}_i = \{hp_i | h \in \mathcal{V}, p_i \text{ is prime and } hp_i \text{ is not divisible by any } p_j, i \neq j\}$ for $r = 1$. There are $\frac{\alpha!}{2^{(\alpha-2)}}$ blocks for $r = 1$ represented as $\mathcal{B}_{ij} = \{hp_i | h \in \mathcal{V}, p_i \text{ and } p_j \text{ are any two distinct primes and } hp_i \text{ and } hp_j \text{ are not divisible by any } p_k, k \neq i, j\}$. Continuing in this way we get total

$\prod_{i=1}^n (s_i + 1) - 1$ indiscernibility classes.

Example 3.9 Consider the power graph $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_{12}$, where

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$m = 2^2 \cdot 3$ having vertex set $\mathcal{G} = \{0,1,2,3,\dots,12\}$. We get $\mathbb{C}(0)|\mathbb{C}(2)|\mathbb{C}(3)|\mathbb{C}(4)|\mathbb{C}(6)$. Therefore, $|\pi_{\mathcal{G}}| = (3)(2) - 1$.

Proposition 3.10 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}, s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} . Then number of elements in a saturated class will be $\prod_{i=1}^m \phi(p_i) + 1$.

Proposition 3.11 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}, s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} . Then number of elements in a classes except the saturated class are $\prod_{i=1}^m \phi(p_i^c)$.

Example 3.12 $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_{2 \times 3 \times 7} = \mathcal{Z}_{42} = \{0,1,2,3,\dots,41\}$ be a group. Then the classes of $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ and number of elements in each class are given by;

$$\mathbb{C}(1) = \{0,1,5,11,13,17,19,23,25,29,31,37,41\} = (\phi(p_1)\phi(p_2)\phi(p_3) + 1).$$

$$\mathbb{C}(p_1) = \mathbb{C}(2) = \{2,4,8,10,16,20,22,26,32,34,38,40\} = \phi(p_2 p_3).$$

$$\mathbb{C}(p_2) = \mathbb{C}(3) = \{3,9,15,27,33,39\} = \phi(p_1 p_3).$$

$$\mathbb{C}(p_3) = \mathbb{C}(7) = \{7,35\} = \phi(p_1 p_2).$$

$$\mathbb{C}(p_1 p_2) = \mathbb{C}(6) = \{6,12,18,24,30,36\} = \phi(p_3).$$

$$\mathbb{C}(p_1 p_3) = \mathbb{C}(14) = \{14,28\} = \phi(p_2).$$

$$\mathbb{C}(p_2 p_3) = \mathbb{C}(21) = \{21\} = \phi(p_1).$$

Remark 3.4 Let $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$, where $m = 2p$. Then indiscernibility partition of vertices of power graph $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ consists of three blocks given by: $\pi_{\mathcal{G}} = S(\mathcal{Z}_m)|2\alpha_i|p$.

Remark 3.5 Let $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$, where $m = 3p$. Then indiscernibility partition of power graph consists of three blocks given by; $\pi_{\mathcal{G}} = S(\mathcal{Z}_m)|3\alpha_i|p$.

Proposition 3.13 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}, s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} . Then indiscernibility partition of vertices of power graph is defined as:

$$\pi_{\mathcal{G}} = p_1|p_2|\dots|p_k|p_1 p_2|p_1 p_3|\dots|p_1 p_m|\dots|p_1 p_2 p_3|\dots|p_m.$$

If $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i$, then for $m = 2$ we get two classes p_1 and p_2 , for $m = 3$ we get classes $p_1, p_2, p_3, p_1 p_2, p_1 p_3, p_2 p_3$ and $p_1 p_2 p_3$. Continuing in this way we get the required result.

Proposition 3.14 Let $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ where $n = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}, s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{A}_2 \subseteq S(\mathcal{Z}_m)$ then, $\pi_{\mathcal{A}_1} = \pi_{\mathcal{A}_2}$.

Proof: Let $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathbb{Q}}$ and suppose that $\alpha \equiv_{\mathcal{A}_1} v$. Since \mathcal{A}_1 and $\mathcal{A}_{\mathbb{Q}}$ are the subsets of $S(\mathcal{Z}_m)$ then by theorem 3.2.1 $u \equiv_{\mathcal{A}_2} v$. Thus $\pi_{\mathcal{A}_1} = \pi_{\mathcal{A}_2}$.

Example 3.15 Consider the power graph $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_{18}$, where $m = 2 \cdot 3^2$ with vertex set $\mathcal{G} = \{0,1,2,3,\dots,17\}$ and $S(\mathcal{Z}_m) = \{0,1,5,7,11,13,17\}$. If

we take $\mathcal{A}_1 = \{1,5,11\}$ and $\mathcal{A}_2 = \{0,7,13\}$ then we have $\pi_{\mathcal{A}_1} = \mathcal{G} = \pi_{\mathcal{A}_2}$.

Definition 3.2 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}, s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} . Let $\alpha \in \mathcal{G}$ then;

- (i) α is called \mathcal{A} – inner if $\alpha \in \mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{N}[\alpha] \subseteq \mathcal{A}$.
- (ii) α is called \mathcal{A} – exterior if $\alpha \notin \mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{N}[\alpha] \subseteq \mathcal{G} \setminus \mathcal{A}$.
- (iii) α is called \mathcal{A} – delimiting if $\mathcal{N}[\alpha] \cap \mathcal{A} \neq \emptyset$ and $\mathcal{N}[\alpha] \cap \mathcal{G} \setminus \mathcal{A} \neq \emptyset$.
- (iv) α is called \mathcal{A} – surrounded if $\alpha \notin \mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{N}[\alpha] \subseteq \mathcal{A}$.
- (v) α is called \mathcal{A} – isolated if $\alpha \in \mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{N}[\alpha] \subseteq \mathcal{G} \setminus \{\alpha\}$.

Proposition 3.16 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}, s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} . Let \mathcal{A} be the saturated subset of \mathcal{G} then,

- 1) \mathcal{A} – Interior = \emptyset .
- 2) \mathcal{A} – Exterior = \emptyset .
- 3) \mathcal{A} – delimiting = \mathcal{A} .

Proof: (1). Given $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i$. If \mathcal{A} is saturated then by definition, $\mathcal{A} = \{\gcd(\alpha, m) = 1, \forall \alpha \in \mathcal{G} \cup \{0\}\}$. Since \mathcal{A} is saturated. So, $\mathcal{N}[\alpha_i] = \mathcal{Z}_m, \forall \alpha_i \in \mathcal{A}$. Thus by definition \mathcal{A} – Interior = \emptyset . (2). Since by (1) $\mathcal{N}[\alpha_i] = \mathcal{A}, \forall \alpha_i \in \mathcal{A}$. Let $\alpha_i \in \mathcal{G} \setminus \mathcal{A}$. It is clear by definition that $\mathcal{N}[\alpha_i] \not\subseteq \mathcal{G} \setminus \mathcal{A}$. (3). By previous results (1) and (2), it is readily proved that \mathcal{A} – delimiting = \mathcal{A} .

Proposition 3.17 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}, s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} . Let \mathcal{A} be saturated subset of \mathcal{G} . Then $\text{Iso}(\mathcal{A}) = \emptyset$.

Proof: Given $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{r_i}$ and $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{G}$ consists of a singleton saturated vertex α . Since $\alpha \in \mathcal{A}$ is saturated vertex, then by definition, it is adjacent to all other vertices. In other words,

$\mathcal{N}[\alpha] = \{\text{consists of all } \alpha_i \in \mathcal{G}\} \cup \{\alpha\}$. So, $\mathcal{N}[\alpha] \not\subseteq \mathcal{V}$.

Since α was set arbitrary, thus by definition $\text{Iso}(\mathcal{A}) = \emptyset$.

Proposition 3.18 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}, s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} and let $\mathcal{A} = \{2\alpha | \alpha \in \mathcal{G}\}$. Then \mathcal{A} – Interior = \emptyset .

Proof. Given $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i$, and attribute set \mathcal{A} consists of even number of vertices. Mathematically, $\mathcal{A} = \{2\alpha | \alpha \in \mathcal{G}\}$. Then using the relation of closed neighborhood if $\alpha \in \mathcal{G}$ we have $\mathcal{N}[\alpha] \not\subseteq \mathcal{A}, \forall \alpha \in \mathcal{G}$. So by definition \mathcal{A} – Interior = \emptyset .

4. Rough Approximations and Rough Membership Function

Using the closed neighborhood relation, we address roughness, exactness, rough membership function, and lower and upper approximations in this section.

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Proposition 4.1 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}$, $s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} , where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}$, $s_i \geq 1$. If $\mathcal{A} = S(\mathcal{Z}_m)$, then $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A})$.

Proof: Given $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}$, $s_i \geq 1$. Then the indiscernibility partition $\pi_{\mathcal{G}}$ consists of three blocks using the closed neighborhood relation i.e.; $B_1 = S(\mathcal{Z}_m)$, $B_2 = p$ and $B_3 = 2\alpha, \forall \alpha \in \mathcal{G}$. If $\mathcal{A} = S(\mathcal{Z}_m)$, then $[\alpha]_{\mathcal{G}} \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{A}$. Similarly, $[\alpha]_{\mathcal{G}} \cap \mathcal{A} \neq \phi$ and $\mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{G}=\mathcal{A}}$. Thus $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A})$.

Proposition 4.2 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}$, $s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} . If $\mathcal{X} = \mathcal{G}$ and $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{G} \setminus S(\mathcal{Z}_m)$, then $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A})$. Moreover set \mathcal{X} is exact.

Proof: It can be prove same as proposition 0.4.1.

For power graph $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ with vertex set \mathcal{G} and $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{G}$ is called rough iff $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A}) \neq \mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A})$, otherwise it is called exact. If $m = 2p$. Then the indiscernibility partition $\pi_{\mathcal{G}}$ consists of three blocks using closed neighborhood relation i.e.; $B_1 = S(\mathcal{Z}_m)$, $B_2 = p$ and $B_3 = 2\alpha, \forall \alpha \in \mathcal{G}$. If $\mathcal{A} = S(\mathcal{Z}_m)$, then $[\alpha]_{\mathcal{G}} \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{A}$.

Similarly, $[\alpha]_{\mathcal{G}} \cap \mathcal{A} \neq \phi$ and $\mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{G}=\mathcal{A}}$. Thus $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A})$. So, by definition the set \mathcal{X} is exact.

Remark 4.1 Let $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$, where $m = 2p$ and $\pi_{\mathcal{G}}$ be the indiscernibility partition of \mathcal{G} . If $\mathcal{A} = S(\mathcal{Z}_m)$, then \mathcal{G} is exact set.

Proposition 4.3. Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}$, $s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} and $\pi_{\mathcal{G}}$ be the indiscernibility partition of \mathcal{G} . If $\mathcal{X} = \mathcal{G}$ and $\mathcal{A} = \{2\alpha + 1, \forall \alpha \in \mathcal{G}\}$, then \mathcal{X} is rough set.

Proof: Given $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a group, where $i = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i$. Then using the closed neighborhood relation we have the partitions of \mathcal{G} is $\pi_{\mathcal{G}} = p_1|p_2|\dots|p_k|p_1p_2|p_1p_3|\dots|p_1p_m$
 $\dots|p_1p_2p_3|\dots|p_m$. If $\mathcal{A} = \{2\alpha + 1, \forall \alpha \in \mathcal{G}\}$ then only odd prime's vertices classes $[\alpha_p]|2\alpha + 1, \forall \alpha \in \mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. So, $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A}) = \{[\alpha]|2\alpha + 1, \forall \alpha \in \mathcal{G}\}$ and $\mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A})$ consists of all odd vertices i.e., $\mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{A}$. Since $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A}) \neq \mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A})$. Therefore \mathcal{X} is a rough set.

Example 4.4 If $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_{2 \times 3 \times 5} = \mathcal{Z}_{30} = \{0,1,2,\dots,29\}$ be a group and $\pi_{\mathcal{A}} = 0,1,7,11,13,17,19,23,29|2,4,8,14,16,22,26,28|3,9,21,27|5,25|6,12,18,24|10,20|15$ be the indiscernibility partition of \mathcal{Z}_{30} using the relation of closed neighborhood. if $\mathcal{A} = \{1,3,5,7,9,11,13,15,17,19,21,23,25,27\}$, then $[3], [5], [15] \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. So, $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A}) = \{3,5,9,15,21,25,27\}$. Now for upper approximations $[1] \cap \mathcal{A} \neq \phi$, $[3] \cap \mathcal{A} \neq \phi$, $[5] \cap \mathcal{A} \neq \phi$, $[15] \cap \mathcal{A} \neq \phi$. Therefore $\mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{A}$. It is clear that, $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A}) \neq$

$\mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{G}}(\mathcal{A})$. Therefore \mathcal{X} is a rough set.

Proposition 4.5 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}$, $s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} . If $\mathcal{X} = \mathcal{G}$ and $\mathcal{A} = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_m\}$, then \mathcal{X} is rough.

Proof: Given that $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{r_i}$, $r_i \geq 1$, $\mathcal{X} = \mathcal{G}$ and $\mathcal{A} = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_m\}$. We are required to prove that \mathcal{X} is rough. suppose $\pi_{\mathcal{A}}$ be indiscernibility partitions with respect to an attribute set \mathcal{A} . Since \mathcal{A} consists of primes then, by definition $\mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{G}} \neq \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{G}}$. Therefore, \mathcal{X} is rough.

Example 4.6 For the power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_{12}$, where $m = 2^2 \times 3$ with vertex set $\mathcal{G} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 11\}$ then we have $\pi_{\mathcal{G}} = 0, 1, 5, 7, 11 | 2, 4, 8, 10 | 6 | 3 | 9$ be the indiscernibility partition of \mathcal{G} . If we take $\mathcal{A} = \{2, 3\}$ then we have $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{G}} = \{3\}$ and $\mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{G}} = \{2, 3, 4, 8, 10\}$. It is clear that $\mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{G}} \neq \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{G}}$. Therefore \mathcal{X} is a rough set.

Proposition 4.7 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}$, $s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} . If $\mathcal{X} = \mathcal{G}$ and $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{G} \setminus \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_m\}$, then \mathcal{X} is rough.

Proof: It can be prove same as proposition 0.4.5.

Proposition 4.8 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}$, $s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} and $\pi_{\mathcal{G}}$ be the indiscernibility partition of \mathcal{G} . If $\mathcal{X} = \mathcal{G}$ and \mathcal{A} consists of divisors of m , then \mathcal{X} is rough.

Proof: It can be prove readily by definition of rough set.

Remark 4.2 Let $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$, where $m = 2p$. Let $\mathcal{X} = \{2\alpha + 1, \forall \alpha \in \mathcal{G}\}$ and $\mathcal{A} = \{2\alpha, \forall \alpha \in \mathcal{G}\}$ and $\pi_{\mathcal{A}}$ be the indiscernibility partition with respect to \mathcal{A} . Then,

$$\mu_{\mathcal{X}}^{\mathcal{A}} = \begin{cases} \frac{p-1}{p}, & \text{if } \alpha \in S(\mathcal{Z}_m) \\ 2\alpha | \alpha \in \mathcal{G} \cup \{p\}, & \text{if } i = p, j = p \text{ with } j > i \\ \{p\}, & \text{if } [\alpha_i] \neq [\alpha_j]. \end{cases}$$

5. Discernibility Matrix and Essential Sets in Power Graphs

In this section, we study the discernibility matrix, reducts and essential sets in power graph of a finite group \mathcal{Z}_m are discussed.

Definition 5.1 Suppose that \mathcal{U} is the set of objects that have m elements. A symmetric $m \times m$ matrix is called the discernibility matrix (DM) if its elements at the i th row and j th column have the set of condition attributes as under:

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$$\delta_{ij} = \begin{cases} \{c \in C | c(x_i) \neq c(x_j)\}, \\ \text{if } d(x_i) \neq d(x_j) \\ \{x_i, x_j\} \cap \text{POS}_C(\mathcal{J}) \neq \phi, \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}$$
 Here the element δ_{ij} shows that the objects x_i is discernible from the object x_j by consisting at least one attribute $c \in \delta_{ij}$. Let $\delta_{ij} = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_l\}$ be the element of information table at i th row and j th column.

Proposition 5.1 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}, s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} , and $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{G}$, then

$$\mathcal{F}[\alpha, \beta] = \begin{cases} [p_i^c] \cup [\prod_{i=1}^m p_i^c], & \text{if } \alpha \in [p_i], \beta \in [S(\mathcal{Z}_m)] \\ \beta' [p_i^c], \forall \beta' \in \mathcal{V}, & \text{if } \alpha \in [\prod_{i=1}^m p_i], \beta \in [S(\mathcal{Z}_m)] \\ \cup [p_i p_i^c], & \text{if } \alpha \in [p_i], \beta \in [q_i] \\ \phi, & \text{if } [\alpha] = [\beta]. \end{cases}$$

where p_i and q_i are different primes.

Example 5.2 For information system in table 1, the discernibility matrix is given by;

	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	ϕ					
1	ϕ					
2	{3}	{3}	ϕ			
3	{2,4}	{2,4}	{2,3,4}			
4	{3}	{3}	ϕ	{2,3,4}	ϕ	
5	ϕ	ϕ	{3}	{2,3,4}	{3}	ϕ

Table 3.2 Discernibility Matrix for \mathcal{Z}_6

Proposition 5.3 Let $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i, m \geq 3$. Then $\text{Red}(\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})) = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_m\}$.

Proof: Given that $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i, n \geq$ with vertex set \mathcal{G} . We are to prove that $\text{Red}(\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})) = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_m\}$. Suppose that $\pi_{\mathcal{G}}$ be the indiscernibility partition of \mathcal{G} using closed neighborhood relation. If $\mathcal{A} = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_m\}$ be the subset of \mathcal{G} then $\pi_{\mathcal{A}} = \pi_{\mathcal{G}}$. Now if $\forall \alpha \in \mathcal{A}$ then $\pi_{\mathcal{A} \setminus \alpha} \neq \pi_{\mathcal{G}}$. Thus \mathcal{A} is the reduct of \mathcal{G} .

Example 5.4 For the power graph $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_{30}$ with vertex set

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$\mathcal{G} = \{0,1,2,\dots,29\}$. In this case $m = 2 \times 3 \times 5$. Now indiscernibility partition with respect to \mathcal{G} is;
 $\pi_{\mathcal{G}} = S(\mathcal{Z}_{30})|2,4,8,14,16,22,26,28|3,9,21,27|5,25|6,12,18,24|10,20|15$. If $\mathcal{A} = \{2,3,5\}$ then,
 $\pi_{\mathcal{A}} = S(\mathcal{Z}_{30})|2,4,8,14,16,22,26,28|3,9,21,27|5,25|6,12,18,24|10,20|(15) = \pi_{\mathcal{G}}$. If $\mathcal{A} \setminus 2 = \{3,5\}$ then we have,
 $\pi_{\mathcal{A} \setminus 2} = S(\mathcal{Z}_{30})|2,4,8,14,16,22,26,28|3,6,9,12,18,21,24,27|5,10,20,25|15$. It is clear that $\pi_{\mathcal{A} \setminus 2} \neq \pi_{\mathcal{G}}$. Similarly, $\pi_{\mathcal{A} \setminus 3} \neq \pi_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $\pi_{\mathcal{A} \setminus 5} \neq \pi_{\mathcal{G}}$.
 Thus, $\text{Red}(\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})) = \{2,3,5\}$.

Definition 5.2 Let $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ with vertex set \mathcal{G} . A subset $\mathcal{D} \subseteq \mathcal{G}$ is called essential if:

- (a) $\pi_{\mathcal{G} \setminus \mathcal{D}} \neq \pi_{\mathcal{G}}$;
- (b) $\forall \mathcal{C} \subsetneq \mathcal{D}, \pi_{\mathcal{G} \setminus \mathcal{C}} = \pi_{\mathcal{G}}$

Proposition 5.5 Let $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ be a finite group, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{s_i}, s_i \geq 1$ and $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be its power graph with vertex set \mathcal{G} . If $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{G} \setminus S(\mathcal{Z}_m)$ then $\text{Ess}(\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})) = \mathcal{A}$

Proof. Given $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ be a power graph of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$, where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i$ and $\pi_{\mathcal{G}}$ be the indiscernibility partition of \mathcal{G} and $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{G} \setminus S(\mathcal{Z}_m)$. Then $\pi_{\mathcal{G} \setminus \mathcal{A}}$ consists of single block having $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ which is different from $\pi_{\mathcal{G}}$. If \mathcal{C} is the proper subset of \mathcal{A} . Then $\forall \mathcal{C} \subsetneq \mathcal{D}, \pi_{\mathcal{G} \setminus \mathcal{C}} = \pi_{\mathcal{G}}$.

Example 5.6 For power graph $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_{30} = \{0,1,2,3,\dots,29\}$, the saturated subset

$\mathcal{A} = S(\mathcal{Z}_{30}) = \{0,1,7,11,13,17,19,23,29\}$. Then,
 $\pi_{\mathcal{G}} = \mathcal{A}|2,4,8,14,16,22,26,28|3,9,21,27|5,25|6,12,18,24|10,20$.
 $\mathcal{G} \setminus \mathcal{A} = \{0,1,7,11,13,17,19,23,29\}$. $\pi_{\mathcal{G} \setminus \mathcal{A}} = 0,1,2,3,\dots,29$ and for any proper subset \mathcal{A} we have same partition as that \mathcal{G} i.e., if $\mathcal{C} \subsetneq \mathcal{A} = 2,4$ then, $\pi_{\mathcal{G} \setminus \mathcal{C}} = \pi_{\mathcal{G}}$;

Conclusion

In this article, we investigated the fundamental concepts of granular computing, graphs, information systems, and rough sets. We investigated the connections between groups and graphs and then graphs to rough set. We investigated some rough set parameters such as indiscernibility relation, lower approximation, upper approximation, family of reducts, core, and discernibility matrix. We applied the important technique of granular computing rough set to the power graph $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{r_i}, r_i \geq 1$. Using the neighborhood relation, we consider the indiscernibility relations to fill the entries of the information system and form indiscernible partitions of power graphs. We studied the indiscernibility relations in terms of neighborhood and demonstrate necessary and sufficient requirements for indiscernibility partitions to remain the same and vary when connected with different attribute sets. Granular computing using information system

is described. We investigated the total number of classes of power graph $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{r_i}$, $r_i \geq 1$ and their cardinality. Moreover, we discussed about rough approximations, rough membership function, discernibility matrix, essential sets, core and some topological properties of power graph of group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ where by fixing the attribute set. In future, we will apply the other techniques of granular computing such as Fuzzy set theory to the power graph $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{G})$ of a finite group $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Z}_m$ where $m = \prod_{i=1}^m p_i^{r_i}$, $r_i \geq 1$.

References:

- [1] Abawajy, J., Kelarev, A., and Chowdhury, M. (2013). Power Graphs: A Survey. *Electronic Journal of Graph Theory and Applications*, 1(2), 125-147.
- [2] Alireza, D., Ahmad, E., and Abbas, J. (2015). Some Results on the Power Graphs of Finite Groups. *Sci. Asia*, 41(1), 73-78.
- [3] Bianchi, F. M., Livi, L., Rizzi, A., and Sadeghian, A. (2014). A Granular Computing Approach to the Design of Optimized Graph Classification Systems. *Soft Computing*, 18(2), 393-412.
- [4] Bosak, J. (1964). The Graphs of Semi-groups. *Theory of Graphs and Application*, 119-125.
- [5] Cattaneo, G., Chiaselotti, G., Ciucci, D., and Gentile, T. (2016). On the Connection of Hypergraph Theory with Formal Concept Analysis and Rough Set Theory. *Information Sciences*, 330, 342-357.
- [6] Chakrabarty, I., Ghosh, S., and Sen, M. K. (2009). Undirected Power Graphs of Semi-Groups, 410-426
- [7] Chen, J., and Li, J. (2012). An Application of Rough Sets to Graph Theory. *Information Sciences*, 201, 114-127.
- [8] Chen, G., and Zhong, N. (2012). Three Granular Structure Models in Graphs. In *International Conference on Rough Sets and Knowledge Technology*, 351-358
- [9] Chen, G., Zhong, N., and Yao, Y. (2008). A Hypergraph Model of Granular Computing, 130-135.
- [10] Chiaselotti, G., Ciucci, D., and Gentile, T. (2015). Simple Undirected Graphs as Formal Contexts. In *International Conference on Formal Concept Analysis* 287-302.
- [11] Chiaselotti, G., Gentile, T., Infusino, F., and Oliverio, P. A. (2016). Rough Sets for n-Cycles and n-Paths. *Applied Mathematics and Information Sciences*, 10(1), 117.
- [12] Chiaselotti, G., Ciucci, D., Gentile, T., and Infusino, F. (2015). Rough Set Theory Applied to Simple Undirected Graphs. In *International Conference on Rough Sets and Knowledge Technology* 423-434.
- [13] Chiaselotti, D. Ciucci, T. Gentile, F. (2015). Infusino, Preclusivity and Simple Graphs. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, 127-137.
- [14] Erdős, P. (1945). Some Remarks on Euler's ϕ Function and Some Related Problems. *Bulletin of the American Mathematical Society*, 51(8), 540-544.
- [15] Fürnkranz, J. (1999). Separate-and-Conquer Rule Learning. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 13(1), 3-54.
- [16] Herrera, F., Alonso, S., Chiclana, F., and Herrera-Viedma, E. (2009). Computing

Online ISSN

3007-3197

Print ISSN

3007-3189

<http://amresearchreview.com/index.php/Journal/about>

- with Words in decision Making: Foundations, Trends and Prospects. *Fuzzy Optimization and Decision Making*, 8(4), 337-364.
- [17] Hońko, P. (2013). Association Discovery from Relational Data via Granular Computing. *Information Sciences*, 234, 136-149.
- [18] Hońko, P. (2012). Relational Pattern Updating. *Information Sciences*, 189, 208-218.
- [19] Kang, D. Li, S. Wang, K. Qu. (2012), Formal Concept Analysis Based on Fuzzy Granularity Base for Different Granulation, *Fuzzy Sets*, 1278-1304.
- [20] Keburia, M. Lexicography as a Political Act. A General Discussion.
- [21] Kelarev, S.J. Quinn, A Combinatorial Property and Power Graphs of Groups.
- [22] Kelarev, S.J. Quinn, (2002). Directed Graph and Combinatorial Properties of Semi-Groups, *J. Algebra*, 16-26.
- [23] Kreinovich, V. (2008). Interval Computations as an Important Part of Granular Computing: An Introduction. *Handbook of Granular Computing*, 1-31.
- [24] Lin, T. Y. (1999). Data Mining: Granular Computing Approach. In *Pacific-Asia Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 24-33.
- [25] Lin, T. Y. (2000). Data Mining and Machine Oriented Modeling: A Granular Computing Approach. *Applied Intelligence*, 13(2), 113-124.
- [26] Liu, H., Gegov, A., and Cocea, M. (2015). Rule Based Systems for Big Data: A Machine Learning Approach
- [27] Liu, H., Gegov, A., and Cocea, M. (2015). Network Based Rule Representation for Knowledge Discovery and Predictive Modelling. In *2015 International Conference on Fuzzy Systems*, 1-8.
- [28] Liu, H., Gegov, A., and Stahl, F. (2014). Categorization and Construction of Rule Based Systems. In *International Conference on Engineering Applications of Neural Networks*, 183-194.
- [29] Mathew, B., John, S. J., and Garg, H. (2020). Vertex Rough Graphs. *Complex and Intelligent Systems*, 6(2), 347-353.
- [30] Mitchell, T. M., and Mitchell, T. M. (1997). *Machine learning*. New York: McGraw-hill.
- [31] Mulkar-Mehta, R., Hobbs, J. R., and Hovy, E. (2011). Granularity in Natural Language Discourse. In *Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference on Computational Semantics*.
- [32] Pal, S. K., and Skowron, A. (Eds.). (1999). *Rough-Fuzzy Hybridization: A New Trend in Decision Making*.
- [33] Pedrycz, A., Hirota, K., Pedrycz, W., and Dong, F. (2012). Granular Representation and Granular Computing with Fuzzy Sets. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, 203, 17-32.
- [34] Pedrycz, W., Skowron, A., and Kreinovich, V. (Eds.). (2008). *Handbook of Granular Computing*. John Wiley and Sons.
- [35] Pawlak, Z., Granularity of Knowledge, Indiscernibility and Rough Sets, *Proceedings of 1998 IEEE International conference on fuzzy systems*, 106-110, 1998.
- [36] Pawlak, Z. (1997). Rough Set Approach to Knowledge-Based Decision Support. *European journal of operational research*, 99(1), 48-57.

Online ISSN

3007-3197

Print ISSN

3007-3189

<http://amresearchreview.com/index.php/Journal/about>

- [37] Pawlak, Z., and Skowron, A. (2007). Rudiments of Rough Sets. *Information Sciences*, 177(1), 3-27.
- [38] Pawlak, Z. (1991). *Rough sets: Theoretical Aspects of Reasoning about Data*. Springer Science and Business Media.
- [39] Qiu, T., Chen, X., Liu, Q., and Huang, H. (2010). Granular Computing Approach to Finding Association Rules in Relational Database. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems*, 25(2), 165-179.
- [40] Quinlan, J. R. (1986). Induction of Decision Trees. *Machine learning*, 1(1), 81-106.
- [41] Quinlan, J. R. (1983). Learning Efficient Classification Procedures and their Application to Chess end Games. In *Machine Learning* (pp. 463-482).
- [42] Qian, Y., Liang, J., Yao, Y., and Dang, C. (2010). MGRS: A Multi-Granulation Rough Set. *Information Sciences*, 180(6), 949-970.
- [43] Shahzamanian, M. H., Shirmohammadi, M., and Davvaz, B. (2010). Roughness in Cayley Graphs. *Information Sciences*, 180(17), 3362-3372.
- [44] Skowron, A., and Wasilewski, P. (2011). Information Systems in Modeling Interactive Computations on Granules. *Theoretical Computer Science*, 412(42), 5939-5959.
- [45] Skowron, A., and Wasilewski, P. (2012). Interactive Information Systems: Toward Perception Based Computing. *Theoretical Computer Science*, 454, 240-260.
- [46] Stepaniuk, J. (2009). *Rough–Granular Computing in Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining* (Vol. 152). Springer.
- [47] Stell, J. G. (2014). Formal Concept Analysis over Graphs and Hypergraphs. In *Graph Structures for Knowledge Representation and Reasoning* (pp. 165-179).
- [48] Stell, J. G. (2010). Relational granularity for hypergraphs. In *International Conference on Rough Sets and Current Trends in Computing* (pp. 267-276). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- [49] Stell, J. G. (1999). Granulation for Graphs. In *International Conference on Spatial Information Theory* (pp. 417-432). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- [50] Stell, J. G. (2007). Relations in Mathematical Morphology with Applications to Graphs and Gough Sets. In *International Conference on Spatial Information Theory* (pp. 438-454). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- [51] Wang, C., Wang, D., and Xu, M. (1998). Normal Cayley Graphs of Finite Groups. *Science in China Series A: Mathematics*, 41(3), 242-251.
- [52] Wu, W. Z., Leung, Y., and Mi, J. S. (2008). Granular Computing and Knowledge Reduction in Formal Contexts. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, 21(10), 1461-1474.
- [53] Yao, J. T., and Yao, Y. Y. (2002). A Granular Computing Approach to Machine Learning. *FSKD*, 2, 732-736.
- [54] Yao, Y. (2007, June). The Art of Granular Computing. In *International Conference on Rough Sets and Intelligent Systems Paradigms* (pp. 101-112). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- [55] Yao, J. T., and Yao, Y. Y. (2002). Induction of Classification Rules by Granular Computing. In *International Conference on Rough Sets and Current Trends in*

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- Computing (pp. 331-338). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- [56] Yao, Y. Y. (2001). On Modeling Data Mining with Granular Computing. In 25th Annual International Computer Software and Applications Conference, 2001, 638-643.
- [57] Yao, Y. Y., and Zhong, N. (2002). Granular Computing Using Information Tables. *Data Mining, Rough Sets and Granular Computing*, 102-124.
- [58] Yao, Y. Y. (2001). Information Granulation and Rough Set Approximation. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems*, 16(1), 87-104.
- [59] Zadeh, L. A. (1998). Some Reflections on Soft Computing, Granular Computing and their Roles in the Conception, Design and Utilization of Information/Intelligent systems. *Soft Computing*, 2(1), 23-25.
- [60] Zadeh, L. A. (1997). Toward a Theory of Fuzzy Information Granulation and its Centrality in Human Reasoning and Fuzzy Logic. *Fuzzy Sets and systems*, 90(2), 111-127.
- [61] Zadeh, L. A. (1979). Fuzzy Sets and Information Granularity. *Advances in Fuzzy Set Theory and applications*, 11, 3-18.
- [62] Zelinka, B. (1975). Intersection Graphs of Finite Abelian Groups. *Czechoslovak Mathematical Journal*, 25(2), 171-174.
- [63] Zhong, N., and Huang, J. J. (2015). Granular Structures Induced by Interval Sets and Rough sets. In *Rough Sets, Fuzzy Sets, Data Mining, and Granular Computing* (pp. 49-60).
- [64] Zhang, Z. (1992). Zhang B., Zhang L., *Theory and Applications of Problem Solving*.